

Long-term data for Europe

EURHISFIRM

D2.4: Involvement of new stakeholders as participants to the General Assembly

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<https://eurhisfirm.eu>

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I. Introduction

Work Package 2 (WP2 - Dissemination & Communication) was responsible for disseminating and communicating the EURHISFIRM project in order to promote its visibility and long-term success. Its goal was to encourage the involvement of various stakeholders as participants in this project. Potential stakeholder groups included, but were not limited to key decision makers, academics, businessmen, and representatives of financial and regulatory institutions.

WP2's main tasks included:

- Developing the project's identity and brand
- Developing of a dissemination and communication plan
- Creating an inventory of European and national distribution networks

In the first year of the EURHISFIRM project, prior to the COVID-19 global pandemic, the intended goals progressed perfectly according to the planned schedule. It managed to complete the following deliverables and milestones¹:

- Deliverables:
 - D2.1 Dissemination and communication plan (M2)
 - D2.2 Website and project identity (M4)
 - D2.3 Inventory of European and national distribution networks (M6)
- Milestones:
 - M2.1 Dissemination and communication plan (M2)
 - M2.2 Project website (M4)

After this successful first year, WP2 was left to work on the last two deliverables **D2.4: Involvement of new stakeholders as participants to the General Assembly (M36)** and D2.5: Presentations of the project at events and conferences (M36).

II. Difficulties due to COVID-19

While serious efforts were taken to achieve D2.4, this proved challenging to achieve due to the COVID-19 global pandemic. All planned outreach events were not able to occur: including an informational meeting in Brussels for interested and potential external stakeholders originally scheduled on the 24th of March 2020. This was originally postponed due to the situation caused by COVID-19, but due to the continuing difficult circumstances, had to be cancelled.

Furthermore, as a consequence of special restrictions resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic, all EURHISFIRM promotional activities and communication had to be moved to online channels. This includes meetings amongst its members and between members and external stakeholders. While the first General Assembly (GA) meeting was successfully organized by WP2 and held at the Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, in March 2019, the subsequent GA meetings were held online.

¹ D1.10

More precisely, the second GA was originally scheduled slightly after the first 24 months of the project, to take place in May 2020 at the Queen's University of Belfast (work package 8 lead beneficiary) and organised together with the Wroclaw University of Economics and Business. However, due to the current COVID-19 pandemic, this meeting was postponed to October 2020 in an online format. The third and final meeting of the GA was held on the 17th of June 2021, also online. It was attended by EURHISFIRM project members, the PAB members, as well as guests (interested partners in joining the consortium for phase II as well as other practitioners from relevant organisations).

Apart from the NEDHISFIRM (collection of Dutch historical financial data by EURHISFIRM researchers and other collaborators) project in the Netherlands, these interested parties include the following institutions that have signed letters of commitment²:

Institution name	Country	Signatory	Position
Leibniz Institute for Financial Research SAFE (Sustainable Architecture for Finance in Europe)	Germany	Uwe Walz	Deputy scientific director
		Muriel Büsser	Administrative director
Luxembourg Centre for Contemporary and Digital History	Luxembourg	Andreas Fickers	Director
		Benoît Majerus	Professor
NOVA School of Business and Economics	Portugal	Pedro Vicente	Head of the research office
ISEG Lisbon School of Economics & Management, Universidade de Lisboa	Portugal	João Peixoto	Vice-Dean for Scientific Affairs
Fondation pour l'Institut de Hautes Etudes Internationales et du Développement (IHEID)	Switzerland	Nathan Sussman	Director, full professor
Binghamton University, on behalf of the Stockholm School of Economics	USA/Sweden	Kristian Rydqvist	Professor of Finance & Economics

This shows that despite the difficulties brought forward by COVID-19, WP2 was still successful in achieving the objectives set out for D2.4.

III. Conclusion

In the third and final year of the project, the promotional activities and (external) communication were especially challenged by the global pandemic. This led to postponement of some key events, such as an informational meeting in Brussels for interested and potential external stakeholders originally scheduled on the 24th of March 2020, as well as the changing of the formats from physical meetings to exclusively online. However, in spite of these challenges, the project managed to proceed successfully and managed to attract new stakeholders as participants. The success of the last GA, held online on June 17th 2021, was exemplary for this.

² D1.14